

The effect of marketing mix elements (4p) on consumers' purchasing decision in Oyo state, Nigeria: A case study of Soda brands

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Abstract: The main objective of the study is focused on investigating how marketing mix elements affect consumer purchasing decision. The research population was Oyo State while the research sample was 384. The study adopted a convenient research sampling technique. The study made use of questionnaire for data collection and two different scales were adopted for the study. The scales include Mittal Consumer Purchase Decision scale and Malau Hamman 4p marketing mix assessment scale. The study has six sections. The questionnaire will adopt a five points Likert scale from section two to section six and the scale will range from Strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree. The questionnaire will be distributed electronically with the use of Google Online form survey tool. For scale reliability, Cronbach Alpha reliability test will be conducted while Pearson Moment Correlation analysis will be carried out for scale validity. The study made use of multiple regression analysis to test the research hypotheses. The result of the study shows that the four hypotheses were accepted. The result shows that product strategies, price strategies, place and promotion strategies all have positive relationship and impact on consumer purchasing decision. Based on the result of the study, the various marketing mix elements have been found to affect the ability of customers to purchase soda. Organizations must invest in the different strategies to help in the improvement of sales, market performance and gaining market share based on the market segment. Marketers must carry out detailed research on customer needs and develop products based on the needs of customers. The product must be a reflection of the society and location. For future studies, the promotional mix should be expanded based on the different promotional strategies which can be adopted based on their impact on consumer purchasing decision. The studies can focus on the impact advertisements, personal selling, sales promotion, public relations and publicity consumer purchasing decisions.

Keywords: Marketing, Marketing mix, Consumer purchasing decision, product, place, promotion and price.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the study

Marketing has become one the most important factors and elements which organizations focus on towards bringing about increase organizational performance and productivity. In these day and age of business, every activity which are carried out by organizations is targeted towards promotion of their brands, products, or services. One of the significant reasons why organizations and firms engage in various marketing activities is focused is on impacting the way consumer behave towards their buying decisions and consequently, consumer buying behavior. Consumer behavior is at the heart of every marketing and promotional activity of any organization. Every product marketer or brand marketer is focused on trying to create content which influences consumer perception of a product and service and also goes a long way in determining how consumer behave and their overall attitudes towards a brand. Organizations invest so much in their marketing activities which brings about increased awareness of the brands and product, growth of their market share based on the

market sector, increase in brand loyalty and brand recognition and furthermore, positive impact on how consumers relate to their products. Marketing activities which include various elements of the marketing process helps in bringing about increase in organizational performance and organizational productivity. Marketing activities is also central in determining the competitive advantage of an organization and also help organizations in gaining certain levels of market share in their market segment. According to Shamout (2016) marketing brings about increase in products and the increase in brands which share similar characteristics, organizations have intensified their marketing actions. The author further implied that marketing activities by organizations in recent times has become intensive due to the increase in market competition between brands who are in the same market sphere. Al-Azzam and Al-Mizeed (2021) opined that organizations are making use of various marketing activities and strategies to help meet their target market niche and furthermore, go a long way in affecting the buying behavior of consumers and also affect the way consumers see certain products and services. In marketing, for crucial marketing strategies are important for organizations irrespective of the products and services. The most important strategy of marketing in the modern era of doing business is marketing mix (MM) which is developed through time from one element to multi elements (Thabit and Raewf, 2018). The marketing mix elements are called the 4Ps of marketing and they include product, price, place and promotion. These four elements of the marketing mix affect consumer purchasing decision in different ways. Many factors directly affect the way consumers act towards different products especially in their purchasing decisions. Different consumers behave differently to marketing activities of different organization. For example, a consumer can see the use of penetration pricing strategy as a bad strategy due to the fact a cheap price attached to a product show that the product lacks quality and other group of consumers can accept the penetration pricing strategy due to the fact that it falls into their budgetary allocation. Consumer purchasing decision is a major issue in marketing which goes a long way in determining the various actions of organizations in marketing their products. In Nigeria, consumer purchasing decision is influenced by the brand, the price of the product, the availability of the product and most especially, the promotional strategies used in promoting the product. Marketing in Nigeria is a big conundrum due to the disparities in the different segments of customers in Nigeria (Obasan et al., 2015). This study is focused on analyzing the impact of the various marketing mix elements on consumer purchasing decision.

1.2 Research aim and objectives

The aim of the study is focused on investigating how marketing mix elements affect consumer purchasing decision.

Other objectives include:

- i. To examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on product.
- ii. To examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on price.
- iii. To investigate the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on promotional activities.
- iv. To examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision as regards place and distribution actions.

1.3 Research hypotheses

H1: Product strategy has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H2: Pricing strategy has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H3: Promotional strategy has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria.

H4: Place strategy has a positive effect on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria.

1.4 Research gap

Consumer purchasing decision is an important area of study which organizations must focus on especially when it relates to the marketing their products and services. The need for intensive market research before products development and launch cannot be overemphasized in any organization. The result of the study will be important to marketers in Nigeria and organizations doing business in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Defining Marketing

In defining marketing, Iwu (2009:10) quoting a definition from the American Marketing Association wrote that marketing is the process of planning and executing the idea generation or conception, pricing, promotion or distribution of ideas,

goods and services which is aimed at creating exchanges towards personal and organizational satisfaction. Furthermore, marketing focuses on the process of making decision which are directed at meeting the needs of consumers and organizations. In defining the concept of marketing, Brunswick (2014:33) stated that the major definition of marketing focuses on organizing and planning of firm’s customer-impinging resources policies and activities with the view of satisfying the needs and wants of chosen customer groups at a profit. This definition of marketing was based on Kotler. Marketing focuses on creating a bridge between producers and consumers. Contreras and Ramos (2015) stated marketing focuses on determining the needs of a specific segment or market niche and taking into consideration of many factors to help meet the needs of the target group better than anyone. Marketing is just about anticipating and needs of customers, satisfying the needs through the exchange of resources which is mutually beneficial (Iwu, 2009). The major reasoning behind marketing is geared towards exchanging, sharing information, engaging in conversations and instigating interventions towards improving the quality of goods and services as well as to obtain some benefits (Gillannia et al., 2013).

2.2 Marketing Mix (MM)

Marketing mix are set of tools which are controllable and organizations blend in synergy to bring about needed response based on the target market (Al Badi., 2018). The major objective of the marketing mix is to meet the needs and wants of the organization’s target market or market segment. According to Thabit and Raewf (2018), marketing mix is a conceptual framework which helps in clarifying the main decisions managers make arranging their product or service offerings to meet the needs of consumers and also help in increase consumer loyalty based on consumer satisfaction. It is the most important framework which is adopted by marketers to provide consumers with their specific needs. (Gio, 2018). Cengiz and Yayla (2008) stated that the advantage of the concept is that the various aspects of marketing are fixed into one matrix and this help in making marketing to be easier. It helps in the separation of marketing from the activities of the organization.

2.2.1 Elements of the marketing mix

Product	Place	Price	Promotion
Quality	Channels	Pricing strategy	Advertising
Features	Coverage	Discounts	Personal selling
Design	Locations	Allowances	Publicity
Style		Handling charges	Displays

Figure 2.1: Marketing Mix Element (Source: Gilaninia et al 2013).

Based on the figure above, Marketing mix is essentially made up of four elements which are interrelated. The four elements work together to optimize the marketing activities of any organization that is adopting the marketing mix (MM) framework (Al Badi 2018). They include product, price, place and promotion. Product is anything which is used to gain attention of consumers (Gilaninia et al., 2013). Product includes a design, a technology, ability being provided and value targeted. It is essentially the most important marketing element (Cengiz and Yayla., 2008). Gilaninia et al. (2013) stated that price element in the marketing mix focuses on the actual amount of money which is exchanged for a said product, goods or services. Price is an important aspect of the marketing process because it provides a sense of value of the product from both the different groups. Place consist of all the processes through which the services and goods of the manufacturer is brought to the consumer (Al Badi., 2018). It focuses on product distribution and distribution channels include different agents, dealers, processing warehousing, materials handling, inventory management and transportation (Goi., 2015). Promotion focuses on taking or delivering the message based on the products and services to the intended audience (Gilaninia et al., 2013). It involves advertisement, sales promotion and sponsorship, use of sales incentives, private sale, public relations and direct marketing.

Product Mix	Place Mix
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality • Design • Variety • Branding • Features • Packaging • Warranty • Service 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agent • Wholesaler • Retailer • Warehousing • Transportation • Inventory management
Price Mix	Promotion Mix
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Price substitute of goods • Commission • Discount • Terms of sales • Allowances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal selling • Sales promotion • Advertising • Public relation • Publicity

Figure 2.2: Overview of the functions of the marketing mix element (Source: Al Badi, 2018).

2.3 Consumer purchasing decision

Consumer purchasing decision is the last step in the consumer decision making process after all the alternatives have been evaluated (Al Azzam and Al Mizzed., 2021). Purchasing decision made by consumer is affected based on various factors in the decision making process. Every process and step in the decision making process all leads to the stages of making a purchase which is the sixth while review of the decision and consequences of the decision made is the last step. The stages in the decision making process include, identification of the decision of problem, gathering of important information, identification of various alternatives, weigh-in the evidence, choose among alternatives, purchasing decision and finally, review of decision made (Mirabi, Hamed and Hamid., 2015). Consumer purchasing decision process in the various processes which is involved when consumer exchanges money for a product or service (Qazzafi., 2019). Consumer purchasing decision process is based on consumer overall behavior which is focused on explaining why consumers need certain products, what they need, when the product is needed and how to buy the product. Purchase decision involves a sequence of choices which are formed by a consumer before a purchase is made and these sequence of choices starts from the point of consumer willingness to fulfill a need (Hanaysha et al., 2017). Consumer purchasing decision is affected by personal factors, which include individual traits and personal characteristics that helps in shaping the purchasing decision making process of customers (Qazzafi, 2020). Narci (2021) found out that consumer perception which is an element of consumer person traits play a huge role in consumer purchasing decision and re-purchasing intention. It is also affected by psychological factors. This factor focuses on how the mind works which is based on the psyche of the individual (Qazzafi, 2020). This factor is broadly known as the internal factor which is focused on the inner workings of the mind of the individual (Hanaysha., 2017:25). It involves social factor and this factor focuses on the influence of social interaction which can include influence of a group, social network of an individual, online social network and family or an individual (Hanaysha.,2017). Economic factor is the fourth factor which affect consumer purchasing decision (Abumalloh et al., 2018:20). The author stated that the economic situation and position where a consumer finds his or herself affect the decision-making process of consumer. It also effects the choice of a specific product in an alternative of many brands.

2.4 Relationship between marketing mix and consumer purchasing decision

Product mix which focuses on the quality of the product, design of the product, variety of the product, branding carried out on the product, features of the product, packaging of the product or the service being rendered and the service provided affect consumer purchasing decision process (Al Badi., 2018:28). These are psychological factors especially the packaging of the product, the design of the product and the products in the product line. Factors which are associated to the product element which affect consumer purchasing decision include product variety, product line, product quality, product design, the various factors of the product, brand, product packaging and size of the product (Gilaninia et al., 2013:29). Abumalloh et al (2018:25) found out in a study that pricing strategy which are used fall into either psychological factor or economic factor based on consumer purchasing decision. The author further wrote that the

economic situation and position where a consumer finds his or herself affect the decision-making process of consumer based on the purchase. The pricing strategies which are used by marketers and the various elements of the pricing mix affects the buying decision of employees. It also effects the choice of a specific product in an alternative of many brands. Al Badi (2018) stated that price help in creating a certain form of product differentiation among customers. Based on price, customers go for lesser brands or higher brands based on their income or how much they are willing to pay for a product. Zhao et al (2021) found out in a study that the pricing technique which is adopted in a study goes a long way in the way customers carry out their purchase. The author analyzed the use of odd/even pricing and the role they play in determining how customers buy. Marketers in recent times have researched and adopted psychological pricing techniques and this have been found to affect the psych of buyers. Odd-Even pricing and competitive pricing are major examples of psychological pricing and they have been found to have certain form of effect in the way customers make their purchase and their intent to buy. Promotional factors are one of the most important which helps in swaying consumer purchasing behavior. According to Thabit and Raewf (2018), promotion helps in persuading the consumers and influence the buying decision on consumers. Al Badi (2018) in a similar study found out that it is one of the most powerful elements based on the marketing mix. Promotion is a social factor which affect consumer purchasing decisions. The purpose of making or producing a product is for it to be sold to consumers and furthermore, the product or services must be made ready to the consumer at a suitable place based and accessibility (Thabit and Raewf., 2018:124). Based on this, the author found out that the place mix affect the purchasing decisions of consumer

2.5 Conceptual framework

The figure below is the conceptual framework for the study

Figure 2.3: Conceptual framework

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a case study research design. The case study design will be adopted to study the relationship which exist between the marketing mix and consumer purchasing decision as related to consumption in Oyo state, Nigeria. The population of the study was consumers in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a convenient sampling technique with the use of 384 participants (ideal sample size considering a 95% confidence interval and a 5% margin of error will be 384). The adopted a primary mode of data collection with the use of questionnaires. The questionnaire compose of 6 sections. The study made use of two scales, Mittal Consumer Purchase Decision scale and Malau Hamman 4p marketing mix assessment scale. The questionnaire adopted a five points Likert scale from section two to section six and the scale will range from Strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree and strongly agree. The questionnaire was distributed electronically with the use of Google Online form survey tool. Participants were provided with consent forms too. Cronbach's Alpha reliability test will be used to check the internal reliability. The adopted a descriptive case study design. The study adopted a descriptive and inferential analysis in the empirical analysis. For the demographic characteristics, the study adopted a descriptive analysis with the use of mean, standard deviation, Skewness, Kurkosis and frequency distribution. For the test of hypothesis, the study adopted a Multiple Regression Analysis.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Descriptive statistics

Table 4.1: Descriptive statistics of participants

	Age interval	Gender	Marital status	Household income (monthly)
Mean	2.86	1.56	1.52	1.76
Std. Error of Mean	0.062	0.025	0.025	0.034
Std. Deviation	1.239	0.497	0.500	0.432
Variance	1.535	0.247	0.250	0.450
Std. Error of Skewness	0.122	0.122	0.122	0.122
Kurtosis	-0.928	-1.943	-2.004	-2.786
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.243	0.243	0.243	0.243
Range	4	1	1	4

The descriptive statistics of the demographic characteristics of participants were discussed. The mean of age interval was found to be the highest mean with 2.86 and this shows that most of the participants are between the ages of 24 years – 29 years and 30 years – 35 years. The gender of participants in the study shows that more female participated in the study compared to male. The mean for marital status was also 1.52 and it indicates that more married people participated in the study compared to single participants. Based on household income, the mean of the distribution shows that most participants of the study were between the income range of N200,000 – N300,000 and N300,000 – N400,000. The mean score for the different variables are 2.86, 1.56, 1.52 and 1.76 for, age interval, gender, marital status and household income respectively

4.2 Reliability of scales

Table 4.2: Scale reliability

Scales	Coefficient	No of items
Purchase Decision scale	0.768	8
Marketing mix scale	0.876	20

Based on the table above, Mittal Consumer Purchase decision scale shows acceptable reliability while Malau Hamman 4P marketing mix assessment scale shows good reliability.

4.3 Test of hypothesis

In a bid to study the relationship and the effect of many variables (independent variables) on a particular variable (dependent variable), the use of linear regression analysis comes into play. The study is focused on understanding the

cause-effect relationship between the different variables. Uyanik and Guler (2013:14) suggested that in determining the cause-effect relationship, the study will focus on understanding the impact of a slight change in a variable and how it affect another variable. Linear regression can be divided into multiple or multivariate linear regression and univariate linear regression. Based on this, the use of multiple regression will be adopted in determining the relationship between product, price, place and promotion strategies on consumer purchasing decisions. Mathematically, the equation for the study is;

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \dots + \beta_nX_n + \epsilon$$

Y = dependent variable;

X = Independent variable;

β = Parameter;

ϵ = Error

Table 4.3: Model summary of regression

Model	R	R square	Adj R square	Std Error	Change statistics				
					R square Change	F change	Df1	Df2	Sig F change
1	0.184	0.034	0.022	1.012	0.034	2.753	5	392	0.019

Table 4.4: One-way ANOVA

Model	Sum of squares	df	Mean square	F	Sig
Regression	14.350	5	2.870	2.753	0.190
Residual	408.637	392	1.042		
Total	422.987	397			

Table 4.5: Hypothesis one

Model		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	T	Sig	90% confidence interval for B	
		B	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound
1	Constant	2.056	0.253		8.112	0.000	1.558	2.554
	Product	0.212	0.0079	0.142	2.666	0.008	0.056	0.368

The result shows that product strategy has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions based on the beta coefficient which is 0.212 and P-value which is 0.008 (P>0.05). The research hypothesis which states that Product strategy has a positive relationship on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria was accepted based on the result of the B-value and the P-value. The result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between product strategy and consumer purchasing decisions.

Table 4.6: Hypothesis two

Model		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	T	Sig	90% confidence interval for B	
		B	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound
1	Constant	1.413	0.249		5.677	0.000	0.924	1.903
	Price	0.218	0.084	0.137	2.487	0.013	0.044	0.376

The result shows that pricing strategy has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions based on the beta coefficient which is 0.218 and P-value which is 0.013 (P>0.05). The research hypothesis which states that Pricing strategy has a positive relationship on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria was accepted based on the result of the B-value and the P-value. The result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between pricing strategy and consumer purchasing decisions.

Table 4.7: Hypothesis three

Model		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	T	Sig	90% confidence interval for B	
		B	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound
1	Constant	1.838	0.255		7.198	0.000	1.336	2.340
	Place	0.134	0.099	0.072	1.342	0.018	-0.062	0.326

The result shows that place strategy has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions based on the beta coefficient which is 0.134 and P-value which is 0.018 ($P > 0.05$). The research hypothesis which states that place strategy has a positive relationship on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria was accepted based on the result of the B-value and the P-value. The result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between place strategy and consumer purchasing decisions.

Table 4.8: Hypothesis four

Model		Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient	T	Sig	90% confidence interval for B	
		B	Std Error	Beta			Lower bound	Upper bound
1	Constant	1.420	0.260		5.455	0.000	0.908	1.932
	Promotion	0.120	0.090	0.070	1.336	0.012	-0.057	0.297

The result shows that promotion strategies has an impact on consumer purchasing decisions based on the beta coefficient which is 0.120 and P-value which is 0.012 ($P > 0.05$). The research hypothesis which states that Promotion strategy has a positive relationship on consumer purchasing decision in Oyo State, Nigeria was accepted based on the result of the B-value and the P-value. The result shows that there is a significant positive relationship between promotion strategy and consumer purchasing decisions.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on this study, an in-depth analysis of the role of the 4-p marketing mix model based on their impact of consumer purchasing decisions in Oyo state as regards to the buying of soda products in the state. The study focused on the buying behavior associated to the different soda brands in the state which include brands from Pepsi cola, Coca-Cola, Bigi-Cola, and a wide variety of other brands in the state. The main objectives of the study were to investigate how marketing mix elements affect consumer purchasing decision in the state. The other objectives associated with the study include to examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on product, to examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on price, to investigate the attitude of consumer purchasing decision based on promotional activities and to examine the attitude of consumer purchasing decision as regards place and distribution actions. These different objectives guided the entire work process, the literature review, the adoption of the dependent and independent variables, the formulation of the research questions and the research hypotheses.

The result of the study shows that the four hypotheses were accepted. The result shows that product strategies, price strategies, place and promotion strategies all have positive relationship and impact on consumer purchasing decision. Based on the result of the study, the various marketing mix elements have been found to affect the ability of customers to purchase soda. Organizations must invest in the different strategies to help in the improvement of sales, market performance and gaining market share based on the market segment. Marketers must carry out detailed research on customer needs and develop products based on the needs of customers. The product must be a reflection of the society and location.

As regards to the market implication and management implications, the result of the study provides ample evidence to show that the marketing mix method of marketing is effective in determining positive attitudes of customers towards purchasing of soda. Organizations must invest in the different strategies to help in the improvement of sales, market performance and gaining market share based on the market segment. Marketers must carry out detailed research on customer needs and develop products based on the needs of customers. The product must be a reflection of the society and location. Market promotion have been found to be one of the most important aspects of the marketing activities. Several

studies have shown that promotion strategies if when properly analyzed and carried out, will increase positive customer purchasing decision and also increase organization performance. Finally, organizational performance especially financial performance is hinged on the ability of an organization of make sales, increase customer loyalty and bring about return purchase.

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